

Intrinsic Quantum Square Root Flux Related Probability of Mutually Exclusive Events

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Classical probability often deals with mutually exclusive events such as a coin landing heads or tails or a die landing on a certain number. There is no information as to which event occurs and so one assigns equal probabilities to each possible outcome i.e. a coin is associated with the probability $\frac{1}{2}$ and a die with $\frac{1}{6}$.

Mutually exclusive events also appear in the quantum world. For example, a single photon moving in one dimension along the x axis in a medium with index of refraction $n_1=1$ may strike an interface along the y axis with index $n_2>n_1$. The single photon either reflects or refracts. If one knew nothing about one probability or another, one might assume the probability to reflect to be $\frac{1}{2}$ and that to refract $\frac{1}{2}$, but there is no symmetry making these mutually exclusive events seem identical as in the coin or die case. One might next suggest that the stochasticity is in the mechanism which causes reflection or refraction, which may be very difficult to ascertain.

For a photon, however, $E=pc$ (E =energy, p momentum and c , speed of light). The incident, reflected and refracted photons all have the same energy, so from the point of view of energy alone, nothing happens to the photon. It is momentum and velocity which change. Thus an impulse seems to occur at the interface such that energy remains unchanged. Instead of suggesting the reflection/refraction mechanism is stochastic, the photon itself may be the driver of the two events, reflection and refraction. If the photon is the probability driver, there is a certain determinism to the problem, but the physical outcomes are probabilistic. The probabilities for the mutually exclusive events add to 1 and so are part of the same equation. If the photon contains an intrinsic built-in type of probability, one would also have an equation containing these built-in probabilities. This intrinsic probability, however, would be one which exists in time and space, it seems. Thus, one would need to match built-in probabilities at a certain x and t . If the built-in probability is a function of p,x,t,E , then weights could be assigned to the reflected and refracted functions with the incident having a weight of 1.

A final issue is to link a weighted built-in probability for say the refracted photon to its physical probability. Given that the built-in probability is associated with time and space, it is not really linked with a probability for an event, but rather with a flux. One may, however, easily associate a mutually exclusive event, say reflection or refraction with their steady state picture flux divided by c/n , the speed. Such a flux does not depend on x,t , but the built-in one does as it is a driver. To link the two, one may suggest that the built-in probability is a unit complex vector in x,t,p,E (Lorentz invariant).

As a result, somewhat deterministic (continuity and links with steady state scenario) approaches may be applied to a built-in flux related type of probability which includes all mutually exclusive events for a single photon and acts as a driver, in order to calculate the mutually exclusive probabilities of reflection/refraction of a single photon. In other words, a built-in type of probability related to flux creates or determines the observable probability of physical events. In the reflection-refraction case, the built-in probability does not directly manifest itself, but in other cases, such as two slit interference it does. The mutual exclusiveness for the reflection-refraction example, however, occurs because the refracted

photon is confined to a mutually exclusive region of space. If this restriction does not exist, as in an n-slit example, the $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ driver probabilities may interfere.

The Idea of a Built-In Driver Type of Probability

A photon moving along the x direction with momentum p and speed c (in a medium with an index of refraction $n_1=1$) may hit a surface along the y axis with index $n_2>n_1$ and either reflect or refract. At first glance, one has no idea of the relative probabilities and might assume these depend on the mechanism which causes reflection-refraction. In other words, all of the stochasticity would be in the mechanism.

Given that $E=pc$ for a photon and that the incident, reflected and refracted photons all have the same energy E, from the point of view of energy alone, nothing happens, although physically impulses occur as the photon momentum vector changes whether it is reflected or refracted. The presence of the interface n_1 to $n_2>n_1$ allows for the two outcomes, reflection and refraction and dictates the p,c/n values of each, but that does not guarantee it controls their relative probabilities for occurrence.

One may immediately write a conservation of probability equation:

$$1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract} \quad ((1))$$

Given that the photon moves and there is a change in speed of the refracted photon, it seems one should think in terms of fluxes, but these apply to a steady state picture (not a single photon) i.e.

$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ ((2)) where AA, BB, CC are the fluxes of the incident, reflected and refracted streams, c_1 the speed of light in n_1 and c_2 in n_2 (the refracted case).

As a result, it seems that ((2)) contains two ideas:

((A)) that of static probabilities

((B)) and at the same time steady stream fluxes.

A single photon, however, is not associated with a steady stream flux unless one thinks in terms of a flux-related probability which exists in x,t and is associated with E,p. This flux-related probability should be Lorentz invariant and act as a driver which can control probabilities of physical events such as reflection/refraction. It, however, has to also be linked directly to the constant value steady stream flux which is the same for any p or E because c, the speed of light is not dependent on E or p, but on the medium i.e. $c/n(i)$, where c is the speed in a vacuum. Thus, using fluxes in ((2)) associates a static probability to reflect or refract with a flow in space-time directly linked to the speed of light.

If one uses the Lorentz invariant:

$$-Et+px \quad ((3)) \text{ together with the form } \exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((4))$$

then one has a flux-type built-in driver (two dimensional) type of probability whose magnitude yields a constant which is wanted for the description of constant flux. Why should such a probability ((4)) exist? It should exist if it, and not the mechanism responsible for reflection/refraction, drives probabilities of physical events. In other words a complex, flux related p, xE, t type of probability largely creates a physical probability (for reflection/refraction) subject to mechanical (not stochastic) constraints due to the medium interface.

As a result, one would expect for the photon reflection-refraction problem that:

$C_1 \exp(-iEt+ipx) + C_2 \exp(-iEt-ipx) = C_3 \exp(-iEt+ip2x)$ at x =interface point which may be taken to be 0. ((5))

In other words: $C_1+C_2 = C_3$. We argue that the magnitude of the probability above should be flux. Then: $C_1+C_2=C_3$ is the same as: $A+B=C$. $A+B=C$ ((6)) follows from the continuity of the flux related built-in type of probability. The static mutually exclusive probability equation (for reflection/refraction), written using the steady state picture of fluxes is:

$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c$ ((7))

If one sets $A=1$, one may use ((6)) and ((7)) to solve for BB and CC i.e. the probabilities to reflect or refract. Thus the driver probability, $\exp(ipx)$, subject to the constraints of the interface (reflection or refraction with p_2), continuity and a link to the static classical mutually exclusive probabilities written in terms of flux solves the problem.

It seems that a built-in driver like probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ solves for other observable probabilities (without using any maximum entropy or equilibration techniques), but rather constraints imposed by an interaction, continuity and the condition that the modulus equals classical probability. In other words, a flux related square root type probability yields what one would expect to be mechanical results (although different from classical mechanics) in terms of a second set of classical-like probabilities. It is these other probabilities which might be used in entropy calculations, although we suggest that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ should be associated with time and spatial entropies of its own, although no equilibration occurs. Rather one somewhat deterministically applies the probability $\exp(-iEt)$ if there is an energy E and $\exp(ipx)$ if there is a momentum p for a quantum system.

An important consequence of the built-in flux related probability is its space-momentum dependence. Momentum is a vector and changes under impulses. In the one dimensional reflection-refraction case, the two media system n_1-n_2 interface forces different outcomes, reflection and refraction, to different spatial regions, hence preventing any interference. (The initial photon and the reflected interfere). This separation allows for mutually exclusive probabilities, i.e. one has a distinct probability for reflection and for refraction which is consistent with a classical view. Such, however, is not always the case as considered in the next section.

N-Slit Device

We argue that an n-slit problem also delivers impulses to the built-in flux related probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. Classically, one has mutually exclusive probabilities because a particle either

goes through one slit or another. (Note: The spacing of slits is of the order of \hbar/p .) The flux related probability type is added for each slit (addition for a probability OR), but impulses may change the momentum vector and probability from any slit may be present at a given x, y outside, i.e. there is interference of probability unlike the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. This ensures one does not have classically mutually exclusive probabilities i.e. one has an overall interference-diffraction pattern on the screen. In other words, one cannot ask which slit the particle passed through.

The driver probability $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is again responsible for the stochastic nature of the problem. It is subjected to mechanical constraints of the slit which deliver impulses. After adding the various $\exp(ipx)$ s from each slit, one may take the modulus to find the classical spatial density, but it is largely affected by the built-in driver probability. (This is experimentally verified.) Again, the stochasticity is built-in to the particle and is not a consequence of the n-slit mechanism which serves to deliver impulses with equal probability for the various p angles because one adds $\exp(ipx)$ s without weights.

Quantum Single Particle Bound State

In the case of a quantum bound state, various $\exp(ipx)$ s are still probability drivers associated with each p and one may consider an average kinetic energy, but it contains unknown weights (unlike the n-slit situation) i.e.

$$KE(x) \text{ average} = \frac{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ p^2/2m \ \exp(ipx)\}}{\{\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \ \exp(ipx)\}}$$

The potential energy acts as a second driver which fixes the $a(p)$ values i.e. $KE(x) + V(x) = E_n$.

In this case, one sees the built-in probability driver give rise to an average kinetic energy which behaves in exactly the same way as a classical, deterministic problem.

Built-in Driver Probability

It seems that in quantum mechanics, a particle with constant momentum and energy has a built-in, flux-related driver probability $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. Given that p , the momentum vector appears, this probability is affected in a classical mechanical deterministic manner by impulses, except now they affect a probability. Given that one deals with a built-in probability, it should give rise to probabilistic or average effects, which it does as described in the above sections, but these are the result of impulse hits which may be predicted without any detailed stochasticity needed. For example, in the n-slit case, an $\exp(ipx)$ taken through a particle slit may have its momentum vector changed in any direction with the same probability, so that the sum of the various $\exp(ipx)$ s may all be evaluated at any x and y point outside the n-slit device. For the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction, one knows that two kinds of impulses are available, one which reflects the photon and the other which refracts, but the stochasticity (i.e. the probability of the two) follows from the built-in $\exp(ipx)$ together with the impulse constraints.

This is very different from the case of tossing a coin or die, it seems, because it is the tossing process which introduces the stochasticity. The die or coin is in a well defined state before being tossed, whereas $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is only in terms of E and p , but not in terms of x and t .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics differs from classical statistics (e.g. toss of a coin or die) in that there is already a flux-related driver probability driver $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (Lorentz invariant) which helps to govern probability outcomes. It is not simply the stochastic nature of the device which renders probability. For example, a coin which is initially heads is tossed. All of the stochasticity follows from the tossing. If one tossed in such a way that heads always resulted, there would be no stochasticity. In the one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon problem, the n_1 - n_2 medium interface may reflect or refract, but one has no idea of what probabilities should be. It is the flux-related driver probability $\exp(ipx)$, which when made continuous at the interface and linked to the mutually exclusive probabilities for reflection and refraction (because refraction occurs in a part of space restricted to the reflected photon), that creates the probability. The reflection-refraction classical probabilities may be used to calculate a Shannon's entropy, but there is an underlying stochasticity in the $\exp(ipx)$.

In the n -slit problem, the slit system may deliver impulses which do not change the magnitude of the particle momentum vector, but change its direction with equal probability for any direction. It is then the driver probability $\exp(ipx)$ which governs the stochasticity of the problem. In this case, there are no restrictions in space, so the various slits are no longer associated with mutually exclusive probabilities as they are in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem. Instead, one has an interference pattern based on probabilities from all slits. The driver probabilities may be added and then the modulus taken to obtain the "classical probability" which has now lost the mutual exclusivity of separate motion through each slit.

As a result, in quantum mechanics, one has a flux-like probability driver $\exp(ipx)$ which interacts with devices rendering impulses. It is assumed one does not need to know anything about probability associated with the rendering of impulses. For example, the n -slit system renders impulses which change the momentum vector direction with equal probability for each direction. The n_1 - n_2 medium interface renders impulses which cause reflection and refraction, but there is no built-in probability. The classical probability follows from the stochasticity of the built-in $\exp(ipx)$. In other words, there is probability (unusual in its nature) behind the more common classical probability (and we argue entropy behind the usual classical entropy).